

Editorial

We are pleased to present the second issue of the *Journal of Economics, Law and Society (JELS)*. This issue builds on the foundations laid in our inaugural publication, continuing to explore the critical intersections between economics, law, and societal dynamics. Our aim remains to foster scholarly discourse that bridges diverse disciplines, addressing contemporary challenges with innovative, multidisciplinary approaches.

The second issue features five diverse and thought-provoking articles that contribute to the advancement of knowledge in Islamic finance, economic sustainability, and the historical evolution of financial systems. Each article underscores the journal's commitment to high-quality research and its role as a platform for intellectual exchange.

The first article, ***“Examination of Sukuk Structures in the Turkish Participation Financial System”*** by Burhan Uluyol and Pashtrik Hajraj, delves into the evolving landscape of Islamic finance in Turkey. By analyzing sukuk contracts and their alignment with Islamic economic principles, the study offers insights into the need for a transition from debt-based to equity-based sukuk structures, advancing ethical and sustainable financial practices.

The second article, ***“Surah Al-Qalam and the Tragedy of the Commons”*** by Haris Lloyd, presents a unique integration of Islamic scriptural insights with modern economic theories. Through a detailed exegesis of Surah Al-Qalam, the author draws parallels between Qur’anic principles and contemporary challenges like environmental conservation and public resource management, illustrating how traditional Islamic values can address global issues.

“Islamic Finance as a Crisis-Resilient Framework: Insights from the Global Financial Crisis,” the third article, authored by Halima Alisic, Betul Dinc, and Anitë Salihu, examines the resilience of Islamic financial institutions during the Global Financial Crisis. By emphasizing Shari’ah-compliant practices and their alignment with the real economy, this study highlights the potential of Islamic finance as a stable and equitable alternative to conventional financial systems.

The fourth article, ***“Adapting to Change: Financial Institutions Among Bosnian Muslims in the Austro-Hungarian Era (1878–1918)”*** by Edin Kadrić, offers a historical perspective on the transformation of financial systems in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The study explores how Bosnian Muslims

adapted to European economic paradigms during a period of significant socio-economic transition, providing valuable lessons on the interplay of tradition and modernity.

Finally, “*Harmonizing Economic Growth with Environmental Justice: Circular Manufacturing Pathway*” by Hazik Mohamed addresses the critical balance between economic development and environmental sustainability. By advocating for circular manufacturing principles, the author provides a roadmap for achieving sustainable growth while ensuring environmental justice, underscoring the role of inclusive and innovative policies in overcoming systemic barriers.

As we continue to expand the scope and impact of JELS, we are committed to encouraging interdisciplinary dialogue and fostering research that bridges theory and practice. This issue reflects our dedication to providing a platform for diverse voices and perspectives, advancing our understanding of complex global issues.

We invite our readers to engage with the articles in this issue, reflect on their findings, and contribute to the ongoing discourse through submissions to future issues of JELS. As always, we extend our gratitude to the authors, reviewers, and editorial board members whose hard work and dedication make this journal possible.

We look forward to your continued support as we strive to make JELS a leading academic resource for scholars and practitioners worldwide.

Edib Smolo

Editor-in-Chief

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